

A NEW DAWN, A NEW DAY, AND A NEW LIFE: EXPLORING TEACHERS' EXPERIENCES IN THE FULL IN-PERSON EDUCATION

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A New Dawn, a New Day, and a New Life: Exploring Teachers' Experiences in the Full In-Person Education

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Abstract

The purpose of this qualitative multiple-case research study was to unfold the multifaceted experiences, copings, and insights of educators during the full in-person education, focusing on their narratives and strategies to combat the challenges and opportunities brought about by this educational crisis during the pandemic. There were seven (7) teacher participants utilized in this study using the purposive sampling technique and each of them underwent an in-depth interview using a semi-structured interview guide to gather data, the study presented a deep exploration of their perspectives and actions. The key findings emerged from the data: unity and collaboration in education and supporting academically challenged learners through collaboration. The findings highlighted the importance of unity and collaboration within the educational community, the benefits of professional learning communities, interdisciplinary collaboration, mentorship, and fostering a positive school culture. The educational findings also probed strategies employed by teachers to support academically challenged learners during the pandemic and stressed the importance of combined efforts with parents and learner-centric approaches. They recognized the vital role of parents in creating conducive learning environments and emphasized the need for differentiated teaching strategies to accommodate diverse learning styles and abilities. This study would contribute valuable insights into evolving environment of education during a global crisis. The narratives and experiences shared by educators offer practical implications for enhancing educational practices and resilience in the face of future challenges in the field of education.

Keywords: *guidance and counseling, remote learning, educator experiences, collaboration, academically challenged learners*

Introduction

The pandemic created a considerable mark in the education sector as it affected almost all activities that we used to do in the past years; in the education sector, the pandemic caused a sudden shift, which made a massive change in the teaching and learning process inside and outside the classroom. With the sudden change, teachers assumed additional roles and responsibilities that were new to them and are crucial for the continuity of education amidst the pandemic; given all the restrictions of the traditional face-to-face classes at all levels, it created problems in delivering quality education across the country. Therefore, the changes caused by the COVID-19 pandemic, which became a global problem, could trigger a new social order or reconstruction (Bara et al., 2021).

As the country tries to return to normal in implementing full in-person classes during the regular everyday learning setup with many restrictions, teachers experienced yet another scenario quite different from the traditional teaching and learning process they used to practice before the pandemic outbreak. It created questions and confusion for teachers and learners and could either affect or contribute to the teachers' practices in this new normal. However, the learning process must continue despite the changes in teaching and learning. Along with the transition, there are plans, programs, and interventions developed by education experts to secure the continuation of the learning delivery despite the pandemic disrupting the teaching and learning process (Hartshorne et al., 2020).

Despite the pandemic threat, the Department of Education (DepEd) pushed through complete in-person education, which aims to normalize classes despite the threat of the pandemic. As part of the new typical setup, DepEd emphasizes shifting learning modality into complete in-person education to address the ongoing learning crisis that results in learning gaps. With the implementation of complete in-person education, teachers are expected to fill in the learning gaps among the learners and elevate the current crisis in the education system brought about by the pandemic. Therefore, it is said that teachers play a significant role in delivering quality education to learners by creating a conducive learning environment despite the COVID-19 pandemic's adjustments and difficulties (Agayon et al., 2022).

Along with the change, teachers' ability to cope with and adapt to the changes that emerge during the pandemic is remarkable. Problems arise in their respective classrooms, but they still manage to deal with it and address it correctly. Despite the change, educators were able to continue performing their tasks to make learning possible, and they are trying their best to acclimate to this new teaching and learning setting. However, despite all the seminars and orientations they underwent, problems inside and outside the classroom still arise due to unexpected circumstances caused by the changes in the learning modality, and teachers cannot simply ignore uncontrolled circumstances as they could directly affect the learning process (Lagua, 2020).

However, during the implementation of the complete in-person education, teachers experienced uncertainty, which raised many questions and doubts on how to deliver the lesson in this newly implemented modality without disregarding the current protocols. As a result, teachers who are at the forefront of this educational problem carry a tremendous amount of responsibility for taking purposeful actions and ensuring that all learners continue to receive a high-quality, inclusive, and equitable education despite the pandemic (United

Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization [UNESCO], 2020).

Numerous research was carried out to investigate the experiences of teachers in face-to-face classes during the pandemic, which affected the global education environment. However, only a few have studied the teachers' experiences, coping, and insights during the current in-person classes. Thus, this study is deemed to explore the empirical gap in research. This multiple case study aimed to gather information about the experiences in complete in-person education. It also sought to identify the similarities and differences between the cases of the teachers in terms of their experiences, copings, and insights during the implementation of the complete in-person education.

Literature Review

Teacher's Experiences

The COVID-19 pandemic has affected individuals worldwide; the outbreak has caused social and economic strife, isolation, social distancing, and an abundance of uncertainty; the pandemic has harmed the educational system, forcing the government to close it for years during the outbreak temporarily. The closure of every learning institution worldwide has created drastic changes in the educational system, forcing educators to adapt new learning modalities to ensure the continuity of the teaching-learning process amidst the pandemic (Agormedah et al., 2020; Khan & Jawaid, 2020).

Undoubtedly, due to the alteration of the teaching and learning process, the learners' overall growth will likely be harmed because there may be minimal opportunities for students to engage and mingle with their classmates during their learning process. The limitations and restrictions could cause problems for pupils who need help to cope with the abrupt changes in the learning environment, as they will find it hard to get along with others inside and outside the classroom (Bernardo, 2020; Tibon, 2020).

Moreover, changes in the learning modality posed a challenge that teachers needed to address accurately, which caused them exhaustion; from preparation to the implementation, many instructions and advice were given to teachers as their guide in implementing a safe school re-opening. The instructions created stress and additional tasks to the teachers that made them feel stressed and exhausted. Agreeably, it was known that in the educational sector, stressors are expected but it has worsened because of the pandemic and the change of learning modality (Cabello, 2022).

Teachers' Copings during the Full In-Person Education

Since there is a need for the resumption of in-person classes despite the pandemic threat, the Department of Education (DepEd) assured that educators should continue to be a top focus in public health and safety initiatives. This concludes the expert idea that educators' mental health and well-being should be a significant priority on a national and international level, considering the implications for educational systems both now and in the future. However, even with the safety assurance, teachers still feel worried about their current situation as they serve as the frontline of the education sector. An expert remarked that this health crisis also challenged teachers' resiliency (DepEd, 2022; Miranda, 2020; Tang et al., 2021; Wakui et al., 2021; Wrighton & Lawrence, 2020).

Indeed, the sudden change in the educational system as to its mode of learning delivery from a traditional face-to-face to an emergency distance teaching and learning setup at the height of the rising cases due to the pandemic in early 2020 formed trials across the school environment. As for the teachers, it has a massive impact on their teaching strategies as they need to adjust their teaching approach to adequately cater to the learners' needs properly. During these difficult and unprecedented times, to get along with the sudden change, educators' top list of priority is to ensure that learners have access is part of the Sustainable Development Goal (SDG 4), which seeks to relieve and leave no one behind, access high-quality, inclusive, and equitable education that fosters possibilities for lifelong learning (UNESCO, 2020).

On the other hand, researchers pointed out the importance of understanding teachers' experiences and how they cope with the changes to create meanings on the ideas they draw from their unique occurrence when returning to in-person instruction and schools reopening. Teachers continue to face challenges and changes and are still in the process of adjusting to the ongoing effect of the COVID-19 pandemic; teaching in-person classes amidst the pandemic holds them accountable for the safety, well-being, and success of both themselves and their students (Bonell et al., 2020).

Teacher's Insights on the Implementation of Full In-Person Education

One of the significant impacts of the pandemic on education is the disruption, which caused a delay in almost all components of the learner's learning process with the threat of the pandemic, even in this new typical setting, hindering the learning interactions of teachers and students. With these, some students are observed to have difficulties in putting their ideas and opinions into words. One of the effects of the pandemic is the class disruption which caused students to have low language skills, and learning competence. The current learning difficulties would affect students' readiness and involvement, support of teachers, classroom equipment, safety and inclusiveness of schools, and system management (World Bank, 2020).

Subsequently, the pandemic has created unprecedented teaching environments, altered teacher routines, and added additional responsibilities. Along with the integration of technologies as part of the teaching and learning process, teachers are already overloaded

during their workdays in areas in which they are unfamiliar. With these, teachers' determination and dedication in their profession were tested. It was found in a particular research that although many Filipino teachers possessed a positive idea about school closures, they are still susceptible to stress and anxiety due to the changes (Talidad & Toquero, 2020).

Despite the epidemic, educators have a huge responsibility to take in, and their role as teachers is an integral part of this new normal. The situation challenges everyone to be innovative in decision-making to effectively sustain the current educational delivery. What is worth studying after returning to normality is the impact of the in-person classes on the teaching-learning process. After that, it is essential to design programs and interventions to ensure learning continuity to aid educational disruptions that will eventually bridge the learning loss caused by the pandemic (Karalis, 2020).

Methodology

The present study utilized qualitative research to explore meanings and insights in a given situation. It was a general way of thinking about administering subject research.

Qualitative study seeks to tell the story of a particular group's experiences in their own words focusing on their narrative on a certain scenario (while quantitative research focuses on numbers). It is a type of research that integrates the methods and techniques of observing, documenting, analyzing, and interpreting characteristics, patterns, attributes, and meanings of human phenomena under study to describe and understand a particular scenario in a study rather than to predict and control a research situation (MacDonald 2012, as cited in Miller, 2020).

Furthermore, a qualitative research study gathers participant experience. It is a method for discovering the individual or groups described to a social or human problem; qualitative studies do not seek to generalize the results to a larger population; the focus is on understanding the concept (Westby, 2021).

In this qualitative research, data were analyzed through thematic analysis, which referred in the form of interview transcripts. In this method, themes were examined to identify their commonalities and differences. Thematic analysis is an excellent approach to research to discover participant's thoughts, beliefs, information, experiences, or values derived from a collection of qualitative data (Caulfield, 2020).

In this study, I utilized a qualitative multiple-case design, to explore teachers' experiences by collecting real-life information from the participants. A multiple case design study explores a real-life multiple bonded system through detailed, in-depth data collection involving multiple sources of information. A case study starts with identifying the unit of analysis, or defining the case differently (Yin, 2018, as cited in Verleye, 2019). Furthermore, Miles et al., 2020 define multiple case research as "a phenomenon of some sort occurring in a bounded context. On the other hand, case research has been helpful in literature but has been underutilized compared to other research methodologies to date (Dillman & Blount, 2021).

Case study research is a robust way to examine the "how" and "why" of complex phenomena within context. Case research has been demonstrated useful but has been underutilized compared to other research methodologies to date. In conducting a case study, researchers can engage in steps to increase rigor, including using multiple in-depth interviews with the same individual(s), using multiple data collection points, and employing multiple rounds of data collection over time with the exact case (Dillman & Blount, 2021).

With this multiple-case study, I identified and explored the cases of the participants. Since this study talks about the teachers' experiences, multiple-case was the appropriate research design wherein the goal is to replicate findings across cases, and participants must be chosen carefully so that I could predict contrasting results based on a theory. Notably, I adapted the rigors of trustworthiness to establish the quality of the qualitative research design and ensure the credibility and reliability of the study. In this qualitative multiple-case design, I conducted a face-to-face in-interview with the identified teacher participants; I utilized interview guide questions to understand the teachers' experiences in full-in-person education fully. Furthermore, I developed the interview guide questions in this study, which were validated by the validators.

Results and Discussion

The findings of this study are not mere abstractions; they are the living realities of educators who have steadfastly navigated the complexities of their profession. They reflect the ups and downs of those at the forefront of shaping the educational world.

Table 1. *Cross-Case Analysis of Participants' (1-7) Experiences, Copings, and Insights to Identify Similarities*

<i>Categories</i>	<i>Participants</i>	<i>Similarities</i>
Experiences	1, 3 & 7	Adapting to Pandemic Changes and Challenges in Education
Copings	1, 5 & 6	Supporting Learners Through Engagement, Collaboration and Integration
Insights	2, 6 & 7	Holistic Approach to Education Maximizing Opportunities and Embracing Growth in Teaching

Unity and Collaboration in Education
Devotion in the Teaching Profession

Supporting Learners Through Engagement, Collaboration, and Integration The theme of supporting learners through engagement and collaboration highlights the importance of creating a safe, conducive, and collaborative learning environment. The sudden shift in education brought concern to various educationalists and other stakeholders about engaging students in times of crisis. With this, various efforts were made to “maintain” or “facilitate” student engagement (Chiu, 2021; Zhang et al., 2021). The theme highlights the importance of face-to-face interaction among learners and teachers to create effective teaching, addressing the needs of academically challenged learners through engaging them in different activities that would add up to their educational experiences, creating activities that would help them to collaborate and work with their fellow learners and teachers integrating technologies to their teaching-learning activities to make lesson effective, efficient and easy to deliver to the learners.

The Holistic Approach to Education emphasizes the importance of integrating all aspects of the approach in education to shape a well-rounded individual. The holistic approach to education echoes the need for educators to employ teaching strategies that will help the learners improve holistically. Though the pandemic has altered the teaching and learning process, educators are trying their best to cater to the learning needs and bridge the learning gaps of the learner by employing teaching strategies that extend beyond traditional teaching and learning to help the learners become well-rounded individuals. Building an education system that adheres to the development of holistic learners in this pandemic era is a must in response to future crises (McKinsey & Company, 2022).

Maximizing Opportunities and Embracing Growth in Education talks about the importance of real-time interaction between teachers and learners to gain realistic results on the learner’s progress. The theme also emphasizes the importance of educators embracing continuous growth and development in education by seeking every opportunity to learn, develop, and improve to adapt to the current trends in education in this new normal. Similarly, educators taking training for professional growth showed higher levels of efficacy in teaching (Dolighan & Owen, 2021).

Unity and Collaboration in Education emphasizes the importance of working together to achieve a common goal; the theme Unity and Collaboration in education highlights the idea of a unified working team that works together towards improvement and success. In times of crisis unity, and collaboration among teachers, parents, and other members of the educational communities have a significant impact on creating a safe, conducive, and positive learning environment for the learners. By working together, challenges can be addressed properly and effectively, resulting in a positive educational outcome. It is through “working together towards progress that donors, investors, school systems, districts, principals, teachers, and parents or families can ensure that students who endured the pandemic would not be left behind, and are not a lost generation but a resilient learner of the new normal.” (McKinsey & Company, 2022).

Devotion in the Teaching Profession The theme of devotion in the teaching profession talks about the dedication and commitment of educators despite the challenges and changes due to the pandemic. It emphasizes the importance of having patience with the learners as they are in the process of adjusting to the new standard setup. Moreover, educators’ level of devotion and commitment during the pandemic shows their passion for teaching and their loyalty to their profession. Their dedication remains despite the crisis they are facing. More likely, teacher’s devotion and commitment towards their profession remains if their sacrifices are valued within the learning community. Moreover, their level of devotion towards teaching is incomparable and immeasurable even during the challenging years of the pandemic (Sahlberg & Walker, 2021).

Potential Decline in the Quality of Education the perspective shows educators’ concern about the potential decline in education in this new normal due to the effect of the recent pandemic. Moreover, teaching in the new normal has its own challenges and threats, and educators are aware of the potential threat of the pandemic to education (Lapada et al., 2020). With this concern, educators express their feelings of worry about the learning outcome in case of sudden interruption during in-person classes. The concern about the current educational status requires educators to be more vigilant, active, and alert in maintaining the current educational status.

Table 2. The Differences in Participants’ (1-7) Experiences, Copings, and Insights

<i>Categories</i>	<i>Participants</i>	<i>Differences</i>
Experiences	2	Potential decline in the quality of education
	5	Tecno-oriented experience
	1	Employing various teaching strategies
	4	Emphasized partnership with parents as a primary coping strategy
	6	Didn’t specifically mention addressing academically challenged learners.
Copings	1	Focused on employing various teaching strategies
	2	Concerns about potential issues with the quality of education but didn’t share specific insights.
	4	Collaboration with parents
Insights	6	Distinct Perspective
	2, 5, 6 & 7	Concerns About Education Holistic and Collaborative Insights

Techno-Oriented Experience educators' experience of becoming techno-oriented during the pandemic highlights their ability to be techno-savvy to deliver quality education. The integration of technology in the delivery of instruction increased during the pandemic when everyone heavily relied on technology to stay connected and updated on the current trends in education. The theme of techno-oriented experience shows an opportunity for educators to learn and develop their skills in using the different types of technology in teaching while a challenge for those who are not techno-savvy. With these, education administrators will be able to create an appropriate program and interventions based on teachers' areas of need for improvement. Additionally, ICT tools, mainly digital teacher competence, and opportunities to understand digital competence are vital in adapting during the pandemic (König et al., 2020).

Employing Various Teaching Strategies Educators during the pandemic find it challenging to employ teaching strategies due to the restrictions of face-to-face interaction during lesson delivery. In this new normal where in-person classes are possible, various teaching strategies were employed by educators to cater to the learning loss during the pandemic. Moreover, innovative approaches to teaching assist the different abilities of the learners equipped with the learning process and teaching success (Carag, 2020). With these teaching methodologies employed, educators will be able to gain insights on what specific strategies and teaching method should be used and how effective those strategies utilized in delivering the lesson.

They Emphasized Partnership with Parents as a Primary Coping Strategy. Involving parents in the educational process has a significant impact on the learning process of the students. The bond and connection between the parents and the learners were evident during the pandemic, when parents served as teachers to their children at home. The Philippine Information Agency [PIA] (2020) shares that parental guidance, support, and presence will serve as an incentive for children to learn.

The theme of partnership between parents and teachers underscores the importance of good communication while working together as a team to build a harmonious relationship that will promote a better, more conducive, and supportive learning environment that will ensure the learning success and positive learning outcomes of the learners.

Did not Specifically Mention Addressing Academically Challenged Learners. Learners during the pandemic find it difficult to get along with the changes in the learning delivery mode as it is new to them, and they are used to the traditional method of teaching and learning process. Educators during the pandemic are dealing with challenges, such as catering to the needs of those learners who are academically challenged, which they need to provide appropriate materials that will make it easier for them to understand and comprehend the lesson.

Moreover, schools have become increasingly aware of the challenging circumstances that some pupils are living in (Power et al., 2020). With the in-person classes, addressing the needs of those learners who are academically challenged makes it easier for teachers as they can employ intervention activities face-to-face.

They are Focused on Employing Various Teaching Strategies. The theme highlights educators' efforts to employ different teaching strategies that will enhance learners' potential as they embark on their new journey toward the new standard classes. It reflects the teaching experiences and student outcomes in the new normal learning perspectives (Vital, 2021). With the in-person classes, educators are driving their focus on gaining the learning loss during the pandemic by employing various teaching strategies that will help the learners grasp the lesson easily. It would also help the teachers to widen their horizons and get along during this transition period.

Concern About Potential Issues with The Quality of Education The effect of the pandemic on education is still evident as educators are still worried about the potential issues concerning the decline of the quality of education in this new normal. Despite of the uncertainty, in-person classes allow educators to fill in the learning gaps caused by the pandemic.

Furthermore, the continuous learning delivery amidst the pandemic shows that education plays an important role and is a powerful driver of growth and development that should be accessible to everyone despite the pandemic (World Bank, 2022). Due to years of school closures, which led to the use of different learning modalities, the decline in the academic performance of the learners is seen during the in-person classes, and it is pretty alarming for educators. This theme highlights the need for educators to work comprehensively to combat the potential issue of the quality of education.

Collaboration with Parents teacher and parent collaboration is an integral part of learners' educational journey; with parents and teachers working together, having a harmonious relationship creates a conducive and supportive learning environment, resulting in positive learning outcomes. During the pandemic, teachers relayed the lesson instructions to the parents as they were the ones who taught their children at home.

Thus, these create a support system for the learners where they can work closely not only with their teacher but with their parents as well. It also creates a bond at home that makes the learning process exciting. In this new standard in-person classes, a collaboration of parents and teachers is essential to ensure learning progress, as experts stated that building a better and stronger collaboration, robust communication, connectedness, and compassion is the crucial part in building back better (Education Scotland, 2021). With these, the need for activities that will strengthen the bond between parents and teachers is a must to ensure continuity of learning even at home.

Distinct Perspective. Educator's perspective in this new standard learning setup highlights their differences in their experiences, copings, and insights. The theme of distinct perspectives among educators emphasizes the various challenges that every educator faced during the pandemic, and it also highlights the changes that they encountered in delivering quality education amidst the pandemic.

Educators' different perspectives on this new normal are rooted in their experiences and copings during the pandemic, as they are not able to do the things that they once used to do as their lifestyle changes during the transition period (Pan, 2020). The educator's varied insights regarding the current educational setup contribute to a better understanding of their experiences, copings, and insights in this new normal learning set-up as it reveals various strategies that educators employed to ensure the continuity of learning delivery amidst the pandemic.

Concerns about Education. In this new normal, educators are still concerned about the continuous effect of the pandemic on education. The theme concerns education focuses more on securing the continuity of the current educational status; it emphasizes the need to become aware of the potential aspects that could affect the quality of education in this new normal. Education reflects what is now and anticipates what is next, recording private and public responses to crises (Žižek, 2020). With this concern, it could be a way to continuously assess the learning needs in education in this new normal.

Holistic and Collaborative Insights. The insights on holistic and collaborative insights resonate with the importance of developing the learners, focusing not only on the academic aspect but also integrating other aspects of learning. Hence, education is a lifelong learning process that requires planning for the betterment of every learner. Furthermore, a holistic approach to education caters to the holistic development of all learners, which must span the cultural, physical, intellectual, emotional, social, and moral domains (Datnow et al., 2022). With this approach, it could have a positive impact on learner's well-being, over-all development, and educational process. Collaboration, on the other hand, allows educators to work with other members of the educational community for a better education outcome that would help teachers and learners.

Conclusions

Teachers' experiences during the pandemic are quite different from what we had experienced during the pre-pandemic years, with the change educators have adapted by adjusting their teaching strategies and pedagogies. Given the situation, educators have to embrace the changes in the learning modality by utilizing the available learning resources they have.

This research journey has illuminated profound insights and fostered a deeper appreciation for educators' resilience, adaptability, and unwavering dedication in unraveling the teachers' experiences navigating the uncharted waters of complete in-person education amidst the pandemic. I have gained a wealth of knowledge from the participants' voices that enrich my understanding of the education realm and hold the promise of shaping the future of teaching and learning in this new normal. Throughout this research, I have discovered that teachers are not only educators who impart their knowledge but also champions of hope and change amidst uncertainty. In the face of adversity, they embraced technology, differentiated instructions, and student-centered approaches to ensure every learner was included.

Moreover, their coping strategies demonstrated the significance of self-care, collaboration, and flexibility in the ever-changing educational landscape. These factors shed light on the needs of educators and the importance of strengthening partnerships and collaboration to build a support system for teachers and learners that goes beyond the pandemic years.

Furthermore, this study has highlighted the importance of collaboration. It has enforced that effective teaching and learning foster strong bonds between schools, parents, and the community. These collaborative efforts could foster a supportive and holistic learning environment where students can thrive and excel. Hence, this study adds to the body of knowledge in various ways. It provides a valuable snapshot of educators' challenges and triumphs. It provides practical implications that educators, administrations, and policymakers can use to foster resilience, innovation, and student-centered education. It lays the groundwork for future research projects that will delve deeper into the pandemic's long-term impact on education, teacher well-being, and hybrid learning models.

Finally, this study revealed educators' indomitable spirit, it also showed education sector's limitless capacity to adapt to change, evolve, and thrive in adversity. It reinforced the idea that education is a shared journey in which teachers, students, parents, and communities all play essential roles in achieving desirable success despite the challenges and changes through working together we can achieve something that could benefit the teachers and learners. Let us carry forward the lessons and insights as we move forward to create a brighter future in which every learner has the opportunity to thrive and shine.

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